

COMPOSITE STRUCTURES ANALYSIS BY THE USE OF A FLAT-SHELL ELEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The advance of composite materials in structural applications has increased the amount of analysis and design in composites field. Available analytical solutions to general shell structures are limited in scope, and not applicable to arbitrary shapes, load conditions, irregular stiffening, cutouts, and many other aspects of practical design. The finite element method is up to now the most used tool for composite materials-based shell structures because of its ability to deal with such complexities. In this paper, a quadratic Serendipity flat-shell element is presented, with layer approach for general shell analysis. The formulation is based in Mindlin-Reissner assumptions, thus considering transverse shear deformation energy. The accommodation of variable material properties, not along the surface of the element, but also through the laminate thickness is made possible by a discrete layer approach. In particular, laminated composite structures with several layers of different materials and different reinforcing directions can be easily handled using this technique. In this paper, the present model is evaluated concerning its performance in the analysis of a typical flat-shell structure.

Keywords : Finite element analysis, shells, composites, laminates, flat-shell

1. INTRODUCTION

The analysis of composite materials structures, specially plates and shells is an area of active research over the last two decades. The finite element method has proved to be an excellent tool for such purpose. Several plate and shell elements were proposed in the past [1-7] for the analysis of composites. Most of these used a Mindlin-type theory for the element formulation.

In this paper, the Mindlin [8] assumptions for plates are also employed for the formulation of a flat-shell quadratic 8-node element with layer approach. The element proved to be very accurate in several tests, with good assessment of both displacements and stresses. In particular, transverse shear stresses are accurately achieved through a corrective procedure [1]. One of the examples that will be presented illustrates the ability of the element to analyse shell structures, specially those with flat surfaces. The performance of the element is very interesting and stimulating, and we expect that the flat-shell element will be an excellent tool for the analysis of pultruded and profiles and honeycomb cells.

2. THEORY

In the flat-shell element (fig.1) formulation, the assumed displacement field in the local coordinate system has the following form (fig.2):

$$\{u, v, w\}_L^T = \{u_0 - z \theta_y, v_0 - z \theta_x, w_0\}^T \quad (1)$$

The global displacements are obtained by transformation of the local displacements into the global coordinate system by the use of a cosine directors matrix [T]

$$\{u\}_L = [T] \{u\}_G \quad (2)$$

Fig.1 - Flat-shell element - Local and Global coordinate systems

Fig.2 - Assumed displacement field in the local coordinate system

By assuming the Mindlin [8] hypothesis for plates, and supposing small displacements, the membrane, bending and shear components of the strain vector are expressed as

$$\{\epsilon\} = \begin{Bmatrix} m \\ \epsilon \\ s \\ \epsilon \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} b \\ \epsilon \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where the membrane components are obtained by derivation of the mid-surface displacements in the local x and y directions, u_0 and v_0 :

$$\{\epsilon^m\} = \begin{Bmatrix} m \\ \epsilon_x \\ m \\ \epsilon_y \\ m \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The bending strains are expressed by derivating the local rotations θ_x and θ_y .

$$\{\epsilon^b\} = \begin{Bmatrix} b \\ \epsilon_x \\ b \\ \epsilon_y \\ b \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial y} \\ -\frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

and finally the shear strain components are obtained through the transverse displacement w_0 , θ_x and θ_y .

$$\{\epsilon^s\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} - \theta_y \\ \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} - \theta_x \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The local kinematic relations expressed as

$$\{\epsilon\} = [B] \{u\} \quad (7)$$

allows the evaluation of the strain-displacement matrix, [B], containing the shape functions and their derivatives to ξ and η normalized coordinates.

The material constitutive relations for the i^{th} layer can be written as $\{\sigma_i\}=[D_i] \{\epsilon_i\}$ or

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{Bmatrix}_i = \begin{bmatrix} [D_1] & [0] \\ [0] & [D_2] \end{bmatrix}_i \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{Bmatrix}_i \quad (8)$$

where $\{\sigma_i\}$ represents the stress tensor for the i^{th} layer referred to the layer coordinate axes (1,2,3) as shown in fig.3, and $[D_i]$ is the reduced material stiffnesses matrix of the i^{th} layer and the following relations hold between these matrix coefficients and the engineering elastic constants:

$$[D_1]_i = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{21}E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21}E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12} \end{bmatrix}_i \quad (9)$$

$$[D_2]_i = \begin{bmatrix} K_1 G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & K_2 G_{23} \end{bmatrix}_i \quad (10)$$

where K_1 and K_2 represents shear correction factors [7].

The stress-strain relation for the i^{th} layer in the laminate coordinate axes (x,y,z) are written as

$$\{\sigma'\}_i = [D']_i \{\epsilon'\}_i \quad (11)$$

where

$$\{\sigma'\}_i^T = \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}, \tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}_i \quad (12)$$

$$\{\epsilon'\}_i^T = \{\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \gamma_{xy}, \gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz}\}_i \quad (13)$$

$$[D']_i = [\theta]_i^T [D]_i [\theta]_i \quad (14)$$

Fig.3 - Lamina coordinate systems (x,y,z) - Local and (1,2,3) - Material (note: z and 3 are the same and normal to the plane (x,y) or (1,2))

where $[\theta]_i$ represents the transformation matrix of the stress/strain vectors between the lamina and the laminate coordinate systems according to the usual transformation rule given in [9]. By integrating the stresses through the plate thickness, the generalized stress-resultant are obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} \{N\} &= \{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}^T = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}_i^T = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{z_i^{bot}}^{z_i^{top}} \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\}_i^T dz = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{nl} [D]_i [\{\epsilon^m\}_i, h_i + \{\epsilon^b\}_i \frac{(z_i^{top})^2 - (z_i^{bot})^2}{2}] \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where nl represents the number of layers, and z_i^{top} and z_i^{bot} represent the i^{th} -layer top and bottom z -coordinates. The i^{th} -layer moments are calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \{M\} &= \{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}^T = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}_i^T = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{z_i^{bot}}^{z_i^{top}} \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\}_i^T z_i dz = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{z_i^{bot}}^{z_i^{top}} [D]_i [\{\epsilon^m\}_i + z_i \{\epsilon^b\}_i] z_i dz = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} [D]_i [\{\epsilon^m\}_i \frac{(z_i^{top})^2 - (z_i^{bot})^2}{2} + \{\epsilon^b\}_i \frac{(z_i^{top})^3 - (z_i^{bot})^3}{3}] \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The shear stress-resultants are expressed as

$$\{Q\} = \{Q_{xz}, Q_{yz}\}^T = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \{Q_{xz}, Q_{yz}\}_i^T = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{z_i^{bot}}^{z_i^{top}} \{\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}_i^T dz_i = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} [D]_i [\{\gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz}\}_i^T h_i] \quad (17)$$

The elastic static stiffness matrix is achieved by the minimization of the internal strain energy [7] and is evaluated by summing up the contribution of the layers as

$$K_{jk} = \sum_{i=1}^{nl} [K_{jk}]_i \quad (18)$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} K_{jk} = & \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^m]_i^T [D_1]_i [B_k^m]_i h_i \right] dA + \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^m]_i^T [D_1]_i [B_k^b]_i \frac{(z_i^{top})^2 - (z_i^{bot})^2}{2} \right] dA + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^b]_i^T [D_1]_i [B_k^m]_i \frac{(z_i^{top})^2 - (z_i^{bot})^2}{2} \right] dA + \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^b]_i^T [D_1]_i [B_k^b]_i \frac{(z_i^{top})^3 - (z_i^{bot})^3}{3} \right] dA + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{nl} \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^s]_i^T [D_1]_i [B_k^s]_i h_i \right] dA \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

This matrix, based on a five degree of freedom vector at node i:

$$\{\delta_i\} = \{u_0, v_0, w_0, \theta_x, \theta_y\}^T \quad (20)$$

has to be modified for spatial structures by introducing another rotational degree of freedom, θ_x . for co-planar elements, a fictitious stiffness coefficient, regarding this degree of freedom, has to be introduced [10].

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE AND DISCUSSION

The geometry, loading, finite-element discretization and materials of a straight girder box bridge is presented in fig. 4. The structure is loaded by an eccentric punctual load. The bridge is discretized, in the thickness direction, by four isotropic layers of equal thickness. In fig. 5 to 8 are presented, respectively, the central displacement of the top flange of the beam, the stresses due to longitudinal membrane efforts N_y , due to bending efforts M_x and due to bending efforts M_y . The present results are compared with obtained by Bouberguig [11] (values in parenthesis). The element proved to be adequate for this type of analysis, being very interesting for pultruded composite design, as well as for general layered shells.

$E = 390000$

$\nu = 0.4$

Fig. 4 - Geometry, loading, supports and materials of a layered girder box bridge

Fig. 5 - Central displacement of top flange

Fig.6 -Generalized central membrane stresses

Fig. 7 - Generalized lateral bending stresses (σ_x)

Fig. 8 - Generalized longitudinal bending stresses (σ_y)

4. CONCLUSIONS

A flat-shell element for the analysis of composite or sandwich laminates is presented. The Mindlin assumptions for plates are used throughout. The numerical example presented suggests that this element produces good results for this type of material/geometry configurations.

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